

**A THREE-ELEMENT, SUPERDIRECTIVE ARRAY OF
ELECTRICALLY SMALL, HIGH-TEMPERATURE
SUPERCONDUCTING HALF-LOOPS AT 500-MHz**

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1. Introduction

Electrically small loop antennas become efficient radiators when constructed of high-temperature superconducting (HTS) materials since the surface resistance losses can be significantly reduced below the small radiation resistance of the loop.¹ Recently, a significant improvement in radiation efficiency (30 vs 3%) was demonstrated for a small (0.04λ at 500 MHz) HTS half loop compared to a gold antenna.² HTS materials can also improve the radiation efficiency of closely packed (ie. < 0.2λ element spacing) superdirective arrays.³ A super-directive array produces a higher directive gain (as compared to a uniform or tapered array excitation) by increasing the reactive currents of the closely spaced elements. For conventional metal elements, increased reactive currents result in increased I²R losses and lower array efficiency. HTS elements substantially reduce I²R losses and significantly improve the efficiency of a compact superdirective array.

2. Single Element Design (Half-Loop over Groundplane)

Figure 1 shows a photograph of a 2" LaAlO₃ wafer containing two TlBaCaCuO HTS half-loop antennas. Figure 2 describes the antenna layout. The half-loop on the top half of each antenna protrudes through a slot in a copper ground plane. An HTS microstrip coupled line matching network is formed on the lower portion of the substrate. The coupled section matches the antenna impedance to 50 ohms. Equations (1) and (2) describe the input impedance of the half-loop antenna.

$$X_{\text{ant}} = (\mu_0 c/\lambda) [L_1 \cosh^{-1}(L_2/d) + L_2 \cosh^{-1}(L_1/d)] \quad (1)$$

$$R_r = 10 [(2\pi/\lambda)^2 L_1 L_2]^2 ; R_L = (1/\pi d) R_s (L_1 + L_2) ; R_{\text{ant}} = R_r + R_L \quad (2)$$

where λ is wavelength, d is an equivalent wire diameter given by d = w/1.15 (determined empirically), w is the strip width, and L₁, L₂ are the length and height of the half-loop. R_s is the surface resistance of the conductor (or superconductor), R_r, R_L are the radiation and loss resistances. In Fig. 3, Eqs. (1) and (2) are plotted

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vs. frequency for the antenna geometry of Fig. 1. R_{ant} is dominated by R_r (desireable for an efficient antenna) and independent of R_s (and hence temperature). This simplifies the matching network design. Equations. (1) and (2) predict an impedance of $Z_{ant} = 0.010 + j75 \Omega$ for the antenna of Fig. 1 at 500 MHz. Superconducting matching networks eliminate residual conductor loss and therefore allow matching to such low values of antenna resistance. Dielectric losses must still be considered however, and will limit the minimum matchable resistance.

The impedance transforming properties of (lossless, symmetric) coupled lines are given by Eqs. (3) and (4). The impedance looking into the coupled line section from the antenna side can be written as;

$$R_m = Z_o Z_c^2 / (4Z_o^2 \sin^2 \theta_m + Z_c^2 \cos^2 \theta_m) \quad (3)$$

$$X_m = \frac{\cot \theta_m Z_c (4Z_o^2 \sin^2 \theta_m + Z_c^2 \cos^2 \theta_m - Z_c^2)}{2(4Z_o^2 \sin^2 \theta_m + Z_c^2 \cos^2 \theta_m)} \quad (4)$$

where $\theta_m = 2\pi L_m/\lambda$, $Z_c = Z_{oo} + Z_{oe}$, and $Z_o = Z_{oo} - Z_{oe}$. For small θ_m Eq. (4) becomes $R_m = Z_o Z_c^2 / Z_c^2 = Z_o (Z_{oo} - Z_{oe})^2 / (Z_{oo} + Z_{oe})^2 = Z_o C^2$ where C is the coupling factor and Z_{oo} , Z_{oe} are the odd and even mode impedances.

R_m can be selected by adjusting the difference between Z_{oo} and Z_{oe} . For a fixed line width this difference depends principally on the separation between the lines (coupling gap). Given the low value of R_m in the present case (0.01Ω), then $Z_{oo} \approx Z_{oe}$ and $X_m \approx (Z_c \cot \theta_m) / 2$.

The reactive part of the antenna impedance is matched by adjusting the length of the coupled line sections resulting in a coupling length substantially less than $\lambda/4$. At low frequencies the coupled-line structure resembles a pi-network of capacitors. Figure 4 contains plots of required coupling gap and lengths vs. frequency to match the antenna of Fig. 1. (In order to accomodate non-symmetric microstrip as well as dielectric losses Touchstone microwave design software was used to generate the data of Fig. 3.)

3. HTS Antenna Fabrication

YBCO Antenna The antenna and matching network were formed from a YBaCuO thin film deposited by off-axis sputtering. The patterning was done by conventional wet-etch techniques. The groundplane was patterned from a second YBaCuO thin-film. Measurements of R_s on these films at a frequency of 22 GHz have given values around 6 m Ω . Scaling by frequency squared predicts $R_s = 3 \mu\Omega$ at 500 MHz.

TlBaCaCuO Antenna The TlBaCaCuO antenna was fabricated on a LaAlO₃ substrate with superconducting films deposited on both sides. The films were sequentially e-beam evaporated on each side of the substrate. After deposition, the composite structure was sintered in a Tl-O atmosphere and annealed in oxygen. Surface resistance measurements were made using a confocal resonator technique, yielding antenna side and ground-plane side surface resistances of 14.2 and 8.4 m Ω , respectively, at 36 GHz. Patterning of the Tl films was performed with a 2% solution of bromine in isopropanol.

4. Single Element Results

Table I below contains a summary of single element measurement results.

Antenna	Efficiency (20°K) (%)	Gain (dBi)	Bandwidth (MHz)
Gold (20°K)	6.5	-7.4	18
(300°K)	2.5	-11.5	
YBCO with gold gnd plane	12.5	-4.5	7.5
YBCO with HTS gnd plane	17.6	-3.0	5.0
TlBaCaCuO double sided	36.4	0.1	0.42

Measurements of the radiation efficiency vs. power level were performed at the input to the matching network for the TlBaCaCuO antenna. An efficiency of 15% was observed at 500mW. At 50mW the measured efficiency was 30%.

5. Three-Element Superdirective Array

Figure 5 contains a photograph of a three-element array comprised of TlBaCaCuO half-loop antennas identical to that previously described. The element spacing of the array is 0.116λ and the element size is 0.04λ . In the initial test array all matching networks are of similar design and optimized to match the impedance for a single element. (Mutual coupling considerations are deferred for a subsequent design iteration.) The superdirective array excitations are rapidly generated via a network of computer controllable attenuators and phase shifters. The excitations are monitored by an HP 8510 Network Analyzer. This configuration permits characterization of both the active and passive impedances of each element in the superdirective array under a variety of superdirective excitations. Figure 6 contains a comparison of measured and predicted H-plane patterns for the three-element half-loop array excited by a constrained superdirective excitation ($\epsilon = 0.01$), which maximizes the signal to noise ratio.⁴ The radiation efficiency of this array implemented using gold elements was measured to be 0.04% (based on a theoretical directivity of 8.7dB). Measurements are currently underway to characterize the performance of this array using superconducting elements. Comparative radiation patterns, array efficiencies, bandwidths, active and passive impedances will be presented and compared with theoretical predictions.

6. References

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Figure 1. Photograph of LaAlO_3 substrate containing two half-loop antennas.

Figure 2. Description of half-loop geometry.

Figure 3. Input resistance and reactance of half-loop antenna vs. frequency.

Figure 4. Required gap-width and coupling length required for matching half-loop.

Figure 5. Photograph of three-element superdirective array superarray.

Figure 6. Comparison of HTS predicted and H-plane patterns for three-element array.